

PROTEINS - THE BIOCHEMICAL ROLE OF THE HUMAN BODY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7451001>

Annotation: The best sources of animal proteins are eggs, dairy products for example, cottage cheese, cheese, granular cottage cheese, fish, poultry, meat. The best sources of plant-based proteins are legumes, nuts, seeds and grain products. A serious lack of protein leads to edema and muscle weakness, hair and skin changes.

Key words: animal proteins, eggs, dairy products, fish, poultry, meat, legumes, nuts, seeds and grain products, weakness, hair, skin changes

INTRODUCTION

Proteins make up about 15-20% of the human body weight, which at a weight of 70 kg gives about 12 kg. The main tasks of proteins are to ensure the growth, construction and development of the body. Almost all enzymes and some hormones have a protein composition. Proteins are actively involved in the production of antibodies and provide strength and activity of the immune system, as well as participate in the transportation of many compounds.

Proteins consist of amino acids, which are divided into essential, which must be obtained with food, and interchangeable, which the body is able to synthesize independently. Essential amino acids for humans are isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan, valine and histidine. Amino acids that are interchangeable for humans are alanine, asparagine, aspartic acid, cysteine, glutamine, glutamic acid, glycine, proline, serine and tyrosine. Different foods contain different combinations and amounts of amino acids.

Animal proteins (egg, milk, fish and meat proteins) contain more essential amino acids compared to vegetable proteins. Unfortunately, the sources of many essential animal proteins are too saturated with fat. Proteins contained in soy, rice, nuts and seeds also have a fairly good amino acid composition.

Some proteins (for example, proteins of grain plants) lack some essential amino acids. Their deficiency can be compensated by a small amount of animal proteins, for example, to cook semolina porridge with milk, add cheese to pasta.

METHOD AND RESULTS

Proteins perform many functions in the body:

- they are necessary for the growth and construction of body cells,
- almost all enzymes and some hormones have a protein composition,
- actively participate in the production of antibodies and ensure the strength and activity of the immune system,
- participate in the transportation of many compounds,
- give food energy: 1 g = 4 kcal.

It is recommended to cover 10-20% of the daily energy requirement with proteins. A person with an energy requirement of 2000 kcal per day should consume: from $0.1 \times 2000 \text{ kcal} / 4 \text{ kcal} = 50 \text{ g}$ to $0.20 \times 2000 \text{ kcal} / 4 \text{ kcal} = 100 \text{ g}$ of protein.

CONCLUSION

The best sources of animal proteins are eggs, dairy products (for example, cottage cheese, cheese, granular cottage cheese), fish, poultry, meat. The best sources of plant-based proteins are legumes, nuts, seeds and grain products. A serious lack of protein leads to edema and muscle weakness, hair and skin changes. Protein deficiency often occurs together with energy deficiency caused by a lack of proteins and other nutrients as a result of a general nutrient deficiency.

Prolonged food with excessive protein content is harmful because it loads the kidneys and liver, can cause gout and increases the risk of allergies. The energy obtained with proteins in the long term should not exceed 20% of the daily food energy.

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